

METHODOLOGICAL APPROACHES TO TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract: In recent years, the demand for foreign languages is increasing day by day, therefore effective ways and methods of teaching foreign languages are being improved. This article describes the methodical approaches to teaching foreign languages, their advantages and disadvantages.

Key words: methodology, direct method, audio-linguistic and audiovisual methods, speech, linguistics, communicative approach.

Introduction.

One of the most important practical aspects of linguistics is the methodology of teaching foreign languages, which today has become a field for theoretical research and practical applications. If you trace the history of the methodology of teaching foreign languages in the last century, it turns out that this is far from a frozen system.

"Direct method" of teaching a foreign language.

The most important requirement was to refuse to train the system. A "live" language used in everyday communication was chosen as the learning objective. By that time, linguists paid attention to the phenomenon of speech, and were closely involved in the study of the phonetic level of the language. It could not affect the technique.

What is the essence of the "direct method"? The main conceptual idea is already taken from its name: students enter the world of the language being studied "directly", that is, how a child acquires his native language. In addition, this means that students do not need an intermediary language, whose influence, from the point of view of the followers of this method, hinders the formation of knowledge and skills. This idea has serious methodological consequences: both the lessons and the textbook exclude the use of the mother tongue. The direct method is basically monolingual. Therefore, special forms of explanation must be developed to achieve clarification and understanding. Thus, a complex system of methods of dictionary semanticization (explanation of meaning) appears, which is based on the rules of lexicology about the interrelationship of words - synonyms, antonyms, definition, description. and semanticization by giving others. Semanticization is most widely used through visualization, which is understood not only as mediation (pictures, pictures), but also as direct (*representation of objects, products of actions, etc.*).

The next main feature of the direct method is the rejection of the deductive approach to the presentation of grammatical material. Regularity, that is, the rule of using a certain grammatical event, is acquired only after mastering speech patterns (phrases) during the lesson and with the help of a textbook through a system of exercises. The priority of practical application of a certain pattern of speech without the obligatory acquisition of theoretical material (*the rule and its exceptions*) is described as the inductiveness of the direct method. In

addition, two more features can be obtained from induction: first, repetition and memorization of speech patterns in this way, listeners imitate the teacher or the textbook. This means another sign of the direct method - imitation. Second, by changing speech patterns, listeners rely on intuition rather than knowledge of rules and act by trial and error. Therefore, in contrast to the cognitive grammatical method, the direct method can be described as intuitive.

The direct method became a springboard for the development of purely specific, highly technical teaching methods such as audiolingual and audiovisual methods.

Audio-linguistic and audiovisual methods of teaching foreign languages.

These methods more clearly reflected the linguistic understanding of language as a set of structures, and also found the psychological doctrine of behaviorism based on the justification of human behavior through the formula "stimulus-reaction-reinforcement". This means the essence of both methods: presenting the language through ready-made formulas (structures) and memorizing them using technical educational tools (speech laboratory, tape recorder, etc.). The audiovisual method is also characterized by the maximum loading of the visual channel for receiving information simultaneously with the hearing aid, which is achieved by showing "pictures" (slides, films, videos, etc.) during the sound stimulus. With this, permanent associations are expected to be formed, and therefore automaticity in the acquisition of speech structures is repeated even when one of the stimuli (visual or auditory) and then the first and second are removed.

Both of these methods are very interesting with their scientific platform. Each step is explained from a linguistic and psychological perspective. Audiolingual and audiovisual methods are very intensive - they require many hours of training, both with the participation of a teacher and independently using technical teaching aids. The goal of teaching, like the direct method, is to acquire a "live active" language.

The hype about "speaking labs" was seen as a panacea for all problems in the educational process. Critics of these methods point out that it is impossible to penetrate deeply into language structures in this way: the technology of the speech laboratory is very limited and therefore allows you to master a set of monotonous exercises, the main purpose of which is to reproduce familiar speech structures. In the development of skills, there is also an excessive tendency towards speaking—reading and writing remain the stepdaughters of the methods and are introduced only at an advanced stage of teaching. As for listening, it does not find consistent development as a distinct skill: with all the rewiring of the auditory canal, listening is a means to an end, but not an end in itself.

An important focal point for both methods is the inductive approach to learning grammar—from examples to rules.

Communicative approach to teaching foreign languages.

With the development of the pragmatic approach in linguistics, in particular, in connection with the theory of speech acts, there has been an increased interest in the mechanisms of communication through language, its communicative function. Linguists focused on the language system and the processes of direct implementation of norms in practice. During communication, it became clear that a certain abstract norm or system is not implemented, but their options are presented by speakers, listeners, reading writers in everyday communication.

Thus, the object of study became what is called speech in linguistics — any written or spoken text. It should be noted that speech is considered not by itself, but in the whole set of factors of its creation: who communicates, with whom, how and for what purpose. The main concept of linguistic pragmatics, and at the same time the methodology, has become a communicative situation, including all the listed and other factors that affect the nature, goals and methods of communication. This led to a real revolution in the methodology of language teaching, that is, it led to the development and formation of a communicative approach, the purpose of which is to teach communication in a foreign language, in terms of its qualities and characteristics, it is close to how its speakers use this language. Since all language operations are understood as an application of the pragmatic theory, the methodological system of the communicative approach considers the learning process as an action produced in language and language. It follows that this methodological concept involves the high activity of students and the loading of the maximum number of information channels as a necessary condition for successful memorization of language information and its subsequent use. The concept of communicative situation is considered by the methodology as a phenomenon that determines the logic of presenting material on the pages of the textbook and in the lesson. All exercises of the communicative approach in one way or another are related to the need to restore the real communication situation, master its parameters and develop the ability to transfer the learned material to all similar situations. Thus, there is increasing interest in various dialogue exercises, role-playing communication situations, role-playing games, real communication simulations.

The goal of teaching communication, as in life, determines a number of points that are very important in communicative methodology.

Real communication situations involve not only "spoken" texts, but also other symbolic systems (road signs, icons, etc.) and printed texts (advertisements, questionnaires, menus, train timetables, etc.). These texts are included in the learning process in order to work with them in the context of the proposed situations. Therefore, in addition to learning a foreign language, we study what surrounds speakers of this language in their daily lives, learn to work with these types of texts — fill out real questionnaires, travel on these train schedules we choose directions, we read real ads from newspapers. Knowledge of life in the country of the studied language is naturally realized in the process of teaching a foreign language. This concept was called integrated country studies.

Within the communicative situation, we act not only as speakers, but also as listeners. The thesis that it is impossible to speak without listening leads to the realization of the need to develop not only the ability to speak, but also listening skills with the help of a special system of exercises and real audio materials.

A one-sided focus only on the situations of speech communication, a great emphasis on speech did not allow to pay enough attention to such types of speech activities as reading and writing. In addition, it pre-defined most of the selected texts in the communicative textbooks. There was a need to return the literary text to the textbook, because it is precisely this that allows to diversify approaches to reading by understanding the purpose of reading the text. Thus, a coherent system of teaching receptive activity strategies — reading and listening — emerged.

Conclusion. So, we looked at modern teaching methods. Is there a common ground upon which all that exists is based? Yes, of course, there are a number of general methodological

principles underlying these methods. But, first of all, it should be said that all these methods have a common educational goal: to teach students to communicate in English, as well as to participate in the formation and development of students' personality.

It should be noted that when choosing a teaching method, you should not only consider your own preferences, but also focus primarily on the age, abilities, interests and psychological characteristics of the audience. Focusing on them, you can choose the most appropriate and effective method.

At the current stage, the following trends in the development of English language teaching methods can be distinguished:

- teaching methods, methods and content are becoming more and more different depending on the goals and planned language proficiency levels, characteristics of the student contingent and educational and cultural conditions;
- stable trends in the reduction of translation methods;
- strengthening the role of student interaction and speech activity;
- use of new technical means in teaching;
- combining elements of different methods in modern educational systems.

Currently, there is no universal method, because the effectiveness of this or that method depends on many factors. In order to achieve sustainable high results, it is necessary to apply a comprehensive comprehensive approach that includes the best elements of various methods..

References:

1. Abdinazarov Sh. Actual issues of education, Karshi, 1991
2. Jalolov, Jamal Jalolovich. Methodology of foreign language teaching: textbook for students of higher education institutions (faculties) of foreign languages / J.J. Jalolov. — Tashkent: Teacher, 2012. — 432 p.
3. Zaripov F. Handbook of foreign language teaching methodology, Tashkent, 2002.
4. Kadirova F. Pedagogical education, Tashkent, 2002
5. History, present and future of learning foreign languages. Regional scientific and practical conferences, Andijan, 2016.
6. Yoldoshev J. Problems of new pedagogical technologies - Public education, 1999.
7. Issues of modern technology of teaching foreign languages. Proceedings of the republican scientific-practical conference, Tashkent, 2007.

